

Economic Analysis of Nutritional Status of School Going Children in Thiruppananthal Block, Thanjavur District

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Abstract

Introduction

Nutritional status during school going children is critical for physical growth, cognitive development, and immunity, acting as a final opportunity to correct earlier deficit. Proper, balanced, and nutrient-dense, and nutrient-dense food including adequate macro and micronutrients, is essential for optimal academic performance and long-term health. highlights the need for prioritizing nutrition in school going children to maximize their potential and contribution to society.

Objectives

To Study the Nutritional status of school going children in Thiruppananthal Block, Thanjavur District.

Materials and Methods

The present study based on primary data. It has been collected from in and around Thiruppananthal Block, Thanjavur District. Totally 60 samples have been collected by using simple random sampling. Data has been collected with help of interview schedule.

Results

The table presents the economic analysis of the nutritional status of school-going children in Thiruppananthal Block, Thanjavur District. The total sample consists of 60 childrens.

Conclusion

Overall, the findings suggest that most children fall within the Normal and Grade I categories, while severe cases (Grade III) are minimal. The data also indicate a slight reduction in severity with increasing age, suggesting possible improvement or developmental progression over time.

Nurtional Status, School Going Children.

Keywords

Introduction

School-going age is very significant because this is the main period of life to make the body store nutrients. These stores help in the rapid growth of children. Good nutrition means a stronger immune system, low illness, better health, and a productive society. More than 200 million school-age children are malnourished, mainly undernourished and about one billion school children will be impaired with physical and mental development by 2020. School-going children are the main contributors to the manpower of the coming time and will help in improving the socio-economic condition of developing countries like India. So, the mental and physical well-being of these children is the most concern that can be achieved by adequate nutrition. The children who do not get an adequate quantity of required macro and micronutrients, including carbohydrates, proteins, fats, vitamins, and minerals (iron, calcium, potassium, magnesium, phosphorus, iodine, etc.) may not be in a position to perform to their full potential in their academics. It is usually seen that the quality and quantity of food in children usually change with time from childhood to adolescence. A healthy diet is not their priority during childhood and poor dietary practices may lead to several health problems.

Objective of study

To Study the Nutritional status of school going children in Thiruppananthal Block, Thanjavur District.

Review of Literature

Since the beginning of the 21st century dieticians, nutritionists, scientists, health practitioners, and policymakers have been finding tools to measure the diet quality, so that dietary assessments can be made for required food quality to the population which is mainly classified diets in two basic categories that are good quality which is rich in fruits and vegetable content and bad and unhealthy foods which is diet contains high fats and processed foods. But it is considered it is difficult to assess the quality of diet in terms of consumption of particular food items, developing a single indicator for the measurement of overall diet quality is a more complex task. But there is evidence supporting the positive impact of individual food items, such as fruit and vegetables, on long-term health and well being, it is increasingly acknowledged that it is the combination of foods that groups of individuals eat which comprise the overall diet, rather than the presence or absence of specific food items, that is ultimate of importance to nutritional health status. As such, McNaughton, SA; Ball, K; Crawford, D, and Mishra, GD argue that analyses of children’s diets should examine not only individual food items or nutrients but also the types of food that make up their whole diet. Researchers have conceptualized the measurement of overall diet quality in two broad ways. The first is food patterns and the second is Diet Quality Indexes. Food patterns are concerned with which foods are eaten in combination and Diet Quality Indexes involve considering the nutritional value of different foods relative to guidelines. There is a growing interest in nutritional epidemiology for measuring diet quality by dietary patterns in place of a single food item or nutrient. The dietary pattern analysis approach implements the fact that foods are consumed in complex combinations and that the balance of the various aspects of the diet is crucial.

Malnutrition is the main global health problem of children which affects large numbers of children in developing countries. Globally, malnutrition is the cause of at least half of all childhood deaths and one-third of child deaths are due to undernutrition only. It accounts for 11% of the global burden of disease. It is more prevalent in countries with low and lower-middle economic populations. Malnutrition among school-age children is a major public health problem. As of 2005, pediatric malnutrition is a risk factor for 16% at the global level and 22.4% of India’s burden of disease. 47% of India’s children are underweight which is the highest in the world and is almost double that of Sub-Saharan African countries. As today’s children are the citizens of tomorrow’s world, their survival, protection, and development are the prerequisites for the future development of humanity.

Methodology

To Assess the Socio-Economic Condition of the children’s households in Thiruppananthal Block, Thanjavur District. To Study the Nutritional status of school going children in Thiruppananthal Block, Thanjavur District. The present study based on primary data. It has been collected from in and around Thiruppananthal Block, Thanjavur District. Totally 60 samples have been collected by using simple random sampling. Data has been collected with help of interview schedule.

Result and Discussion

Table 4.1

Age Group Of Students

Characteristic	Frequency	Percentage (%)
5-6 Years	20	33.33
7-8 Years	24	40
9-10 Years	16	26.66
Total	60	100

Age-wise distribution

The table 4.1 age-wise distribution shows that 40% (24) of the children belong to the 7–8 years age group, followed by 33.33% (20) in the 5–6 years group and 26.66% (16) in the 9–10 years group. This indicates that the majority of the children are between 7 and 8 years of age.

Table 4.2

Gender-Wise Distribution

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
MALES	24	40
FEMALE	36	60
TOTAL	60	100

Gender-wise distribution

The table 4.2 gender distribution reveals that 60% (36) of the children are females, while 40% (24) are males. This shows a higher representation of female children in the study sample.

Table 4.3

Religion-Wise Distribution

Religion	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Hindu	29	48.33
Christian	20	33.33
Muslim	11	18.33
Total	60	100

Religion-wise distribution

The table 4.3 religion-wise analysis indicates that 48.33% (29) of the children belong to the Hindu community, followed by 33.33% (20) from the Muslim community and 18.33% (11) from the Christian community. Thus, the majority of the respondents belong to the Hindu religion.

Table 4.4

Parents Qualification-Wise Distribution

Parents Qualification	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Primary	8	13.3
Middle	7	11.6
Secondary	10	16.6
Higher Secondary	20	33.3
DEGREE	15	25

Parents Qualification-wise distribution

The table 4.4 parents qualification-wise distribution shows that 33% (20) of the parents belong to the higher secondary, followed by 16.6 (10) in the secondary level, 13.3%(8) in the primary level and 11.6% (7) middle level. This indicates that the majority of the parents qualification are between higher secondary level of education.

Table 4.5

Family Income-Wise Distribution

Level Of Income	Frequency	Percentage (%)
< 60,000	24	40
60,000 – 80,000	20	33
> 80,000	10	26

Family income wise-distribution

The table 4.5 family income distribution reveals that 40% (24) of the families earn below ₹60,000, 33% (20) earn between ₹60,000 – ₹80,000, and 26% (16) earn above ₹80,000. This suggests that a large proportion of the families belong to the lower- to middle-income group.

Table 4.6

Nutritional Status of School Going Children-Wise Distribution

Age Group	Normal	Grade			Total
		Grade I	Grade II	Grade III	
5-6 Years	8	5	4	3	24 (40%)
7-8 Years	9	6	2	2	19 (31.66%)
9-10 Years	5	5	4	3	17 (28.33%)
Total	22 (36.66%)	16 (26.66%)	10 (16.66%)	8 (13.33%)	60 (100)

Nutritional Status of School Going Children wise-distribution

Table 4.6 presents the distribution of grades among different age groups (5–6 years, 7–8 years, and 9–10 years) with a total sample size of 60 children.

The overall findings indicate that 36.66% (n = 22) of the children fall under the Normal category, which represents the highest proportion in the study. This is followed by Grade I (26.66%, n = 16), Grade II (16.66%, n = 10), and Grade III (13.33%, n = 8). The results clearly show a gradual decrease in frequency as the severity of grade increases.

Age-wise analysis reveals that the 5–6 years age group constitutes the largest proportion of the sample (40%, n = 24). Within this group, the distribution of Grade II and Grade III cases is comparatively higher than in other age groups, indicating relatively greater severity at younger ages.

The 7–8 years age group accounts for 31.66% (n = 19) of the sample, with the majority of children (n = 9) classified as Normal. Severe grades (Grade II and III) are comparatively lower in this group.

The 9–10 years age group represents 28.33% (n = 17) of the sample. In this group, Grade I and Grade II cases are moderately distributed, and the proportion of severe cases remains limited.

Discussion

Protein. Choose seafood, lean meat and poultry, eggs, beans, peas, soy products, and unsalted nuts and seeds.

Fruits. Encourage your child to eat a variety of fresh, canned, frozen or dried fruits. Look for canned fruit that says it's light or packed in its own juice. This means it's low in added sugar. Keep in mind that 1/4 cup of dried fruit counts as one serving of fruit.

Vegetables. Serve a variety of fresh, canned, frozen or dried vegetables. Choose peas or beans, along with colorful vegetables each week. When selecting canned or frozen vegetables, look for ones that are lower in sodium.

Grains. Choose whole grains, such as whole-wheat bread or pasta, oatmeal, popcorn, quinoa, or brown or wild rice.

Dairy. Encourage your child to eat and drink fat-free or low-fat dairy products, such as milk, yogurt and cheese. Fortified soy beverages also count as dairy.

Conclusion

Nutritional status of school going children in Thanjavur district in Tamil Nadu and all over India and world in general. After reviewing of literature and available data for this paper it is concluded that most of the children are still malnourished even after taking various measures to reduce malnutrition in children so more efforts are needed on the ground level to help the beneficiaries. This can be done by improving Socio-Economic Status (SES) of the families, education level, gender equality, properly implementing government schemes, diversification of food, and active participation of government agencies as well as NGOs. It is recommended that policymakers, parents, and caregivers pay regular attention to the children's diet. The Anganwadi (pre-schools), mid-day-meal in schools, and other feeding programs should be regularly evaluated from time to time and required changes should be made. They should be restructured as per the availability of seasonal food items so the requirement of each food group and Dietary Diversity Score (DDS) and food items from every group (FVS) can be met in children. School health services can play an important role in the development of every child by providing comprehensive care of the health and wellbeing of children during the school years. As health and education are intimately related, the advantages of health education can be attained best in the school. Health education should give more emphasis to preventing health problems rather than providing a cure.

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